

PREPARATION AND PROPERTIES OF A NEW SILICON- POLYTRIAZOLE RESIN AND ITS COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

Polytriazole (PTA) resins are prepared from azide and alkyne through Huisgen 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition. The PTA resins can be cured at low temperature and possess excellent performances, such as good heat resistance and high mechanical properties. Silicon-containing arylacetylene is a promising monomer for polytriazole resin, as there are lots of arylacetylenes in its backbone which can provide the high crosslinking density and rigid molecular chain.

In order to improve the processability, low molecular weight silicon-containing arylacetylene (LPSA) was designed and synthesized from diethynylbenzene and dimethyldichlorosilane by Grignard method. The LPSA was characterized by ¹H-NMR and FT-IR. The results show that the degree of polymerization(DP) value of LPSA is ranged from 1.60 to 1.80.

A new silicon-polytriazole (Si-PTA) resin was synthesized from 4,4'-diazidomethyl biphenyl(DAMBIP) and LPSA via 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition. The Si-PTA resin was characterized by ¹H-NMR, FT-IR, differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). The results show that the resin could be cured at 80°C. The dynamic thermomechanical analysis(DMA) results show that the glass transition temperature(T_g) of the cured Si-PTA resin is 310°C after curing 80°C for 12 h, 150°C for 2 h, 180°C for 2 h, 210°C for 2 h, and 250°C for 2 h. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) results show that the thermal decomposition temperature(T_{d5}, temperature at 5% weight loss) under N₂ and air could reached 342 °C and 340 °C, respectively.

Unidirectional T700 carbon fiber reinforced Si-PTA composite (Si-PTA/T700) was prepared through compression molding. The structures and properties of the composite were characterized by mechanical property tests, DMA, etc. The results show that the Si-PTA composite exhibited good mechanical and thermal properties, the flexural strength is 1678 MPa at room temperature and 1095 Mpa at 200 °C.

INTRODUCTION

Huisgen 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition is an exergonic fusion process that combines two unsaturated reactants ^[1]. And this reaction provides fast access to a numerous variety of five-member heterocycles. In 1960s, Johnson et al. reported that polytriazoles were synthesized through thermal polymerization using 4-azido-1- butyne, 3-azido-1-propyne, 2-propynyl azidoacetate, and p-azidophenyl acetylene as

raw material and the obtained polymer had good thermal stability^[2-3]. However, the polymer was not useful as expected owing to its bad processability. Until recently, triazole polymers have been novel macromolecules that have received growing interest in the area of polymer and material science^[4-12].

Our laboratory has been engaged in developing novel polytriazole (PTA) resins with low temperature curing and high heat-resistance during the past ten years^[13-16]. Some of the resins could be used as a matrix of high performance composites. The cured PTA resin had good heat resistance and high mechanical properties. But most of the glass transition temperatures (T_g) of the PTA resins could not reach 300°C. In order to meet the higher requirement of the thermal performance, the matrix has to have high thermal properties, especially high T_g s. In this paper, a silicon-polytriazole (Si-PTA) resin and its carbon fiber (T700) reinforced composite were prepared and characterized.

EXPERIMENTAL

Raw materials

Glacial acetic acid, Hydrochloric acid, Toluene, Tetrahydrofuran, Acetone, Sodium sulphate anhydrous, Benzophenone (all of analytical reagent grade), Magnesium, Bromoethane, Sodium, sodium azide (chemical purity) were purchased from Shanghai Sinopharm Chemical Reagent Co., Ltd and used as received. Ddiethynylbenzene (DEB) was purchased from Jiaozhou Fime Chemical Co., Ltd and used as received. Dimethyldichlorosilane was purchased from Aladdin Reagent (Shanghai) Co., Ltd used as received. DAMBP and LPSA were synthesized in our laboratory.

Instrumentation

Proton nuclear magnetic resonance (¹H NMR) analyses were used to confirm the chemical structure of monomers, which were obtained by the BRUKER AVANCE 500 (500 MHz, BRUKER, DE.), and tetramethylsilane (TMS) was used as an internal standard. Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectra was recorded with a Nicolet 550 (TA, USA) infrared spectrometer. Rheological behavior was analyzed at a heating rate of 3 °C/min and the shear rate of 0.1 s⁻¹ using a RheoStress RS600 Rheometer (HAAKE, DE.). Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) was carried out on a Diamond DSC (PE, USA) analyzer under nitrogen atmosphere at the heating rate of 10 °C/min. Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) was carried out on a DMA1 analyzer of METTLER TOLEDO operating in the dual cantilever mode under air atmosphere at the frequency of 11 Hz with a programmed heating rate of 3 °C/min. Thermogravimetry analysis (TGA) was conducted on a Pyris Diamond TG/DTA (PE, USA) at the heating rate of 10 °C/min under nitrogen/air atmosphere. The flexural properties of composite were measured with a DDL100 universal tester and the crosshead speed of the flexural test was 2 mm/min according to China Standard GB 3356-1999. The sample dimension was 80.0×12.5×2.0 mm.

Synthesis of Si-PTA resin

LPSA and DAMBP(the molar ratio of azide group to alkyne group [a]/[b]=1.0:1.1) were weighed and filled in a three-neck bottom flask (100 ml) equipped with a stirrer, a cooling condenser, and a thermometer. The monomer mixture was heated up to 70 °C and maintained at this temperature with an oil bath till homogeneous liquid products occurred. A transparent and viscous liquid resin was obtained. The liquid resin obtained was poured into a mold to prepare the cured sample. Then the mold with the resin was put into a vacuum oven for removing the volatile substances. After that, the molds were transferred into the other oven to cure at 80 °C for 12 h for demolding. The postcuring processes of the cured resins were as follows: 120°C/2 h+ 150°C/2 h + 180°C/2 h +210°C/2 h +250°C/2 h. The obtained cured Si-PTA samples were used for TGA and DMA with dimension of 40 mm×6

mm×2 mm.

Scheme 1: Schematic polymerization of LPSA and DAMBP

Preparation of T700 carbon fiber-reinforced Si-PTA resin composite

The T700 carbon fiber was used as a reinforcing material for composites. LPSA and DAMBP were weighed and dissolved in THF. Then the mixed solution was stirred at 70 °C for 4 h to get a Si-PTA resin solution (70 wt %). The carbon fiber was impregnated with the solution and dried in a vacuum oven at 45 °C. A prepreg with resin content about 32-33 % was obtained. A unidirectional prepreg was pressed at 80 °C for 12 h and postcured according to a certain process (120°C/2 h + 150°C/2 h + 180°C/2 h + 210°C/2 h + 250°C/2 h) under pressure of 0.5 MPa. In the end, the composite laminate with resin content of about 32 % was obtained. The samples with the dimension of 80 mm×12.45 mm×2 mm for the flexural tests were made of the laminate.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Thermal behaviors of Si-PTA resin

Rheological behavior of the resin was measured by a rheometer. The viscosity response of the resin to temperature ramping at heating rate of 3 °C/min and a shear rate of 0.01 s⁻¹ is shown in Figure 1. The resin is solid at room temperature and melt at 55 °C. The melting endothermic peak is also showed in DSC curve. At temperatures above 60 °C, the viscosity of the resin was very low and maintained the low viscosity up to 130 °C, which was suitable for composite fabrication. Thereafter, resin viscosity increased dramatically at temperatures above 130 °C due to the further polymerization of the resin. Obviously, the Si-PTA resin possesses a broad processing window because the viscosity of resin is low at a broad temperature region. Therefore, the Si-PTA resin possessed good processability.

Figure 1: Viscosity of the Si-PTA resin against temperature (heating rate 3 °C /min)

DSC technique was used to trace the thermal behaviors of the Si-PTA resin and the DSC curve for the resin was shown in Figure 2 A. As shown in the figure, there are an endothermic peak and two exothermic peaks. The endothermic peak ranging from 45 °C to 65 °C was ascribed to the melting peak of the resin. The amount of exotherm of the first exothermic peak (I) in the range of from 90 to 200 °C was 936.0 J/g, which was attributed to 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition between azide and ethynyl or ethynylene groups to form the 1,4-disubstituted and 1,5-disubstituted 1,2,3-triazoles. The following exothermic peak (II) attributed to the reaction of the excess of alkyne occurred in the range from 240 to 280 °C. Meanwhile, DSC curves and results for the resin at different curing stages were shown in Figure 2 B-G and Table 2. The exothermic peak (I) of 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition reaction became very little at stage B (extent of reaction was 82.0%) and nearly disappeared after stage C. The exothermic peak (II) gradually decreased with increasing temperature, indicating that the alkynyl curing reaction carried on during stage D to F. The extent of alkynyl curing reaction was close to 100% after stage F.

Figure 2: DSC curves of the Si-PTA resin at different curing stages. A. at beginning; B. 80°C/12h; C. 80°C/12h+120°C/2h; D. 80°C/12h+120°C/2h+150°C/2h; E. 80°C/12h+120°C/2h+150°C/2h+180°C/2h; F. 80°C/12h+120°C/2h+150°C/2h+180°C/2h+210°C/2h; G. 80°C/12h+120°C/2h+150°C/2h+180°C

/2h+210°C/2h+250°C/2h;

Curing stage	T _i /°C	T _p /°C	ΔH _I /J/g	ΔH _{II} /J/g	Extent of reaction (I) /%	Extent of reaction (II) /%
A	95.1	153.1	936.0	75.3	---	---
B	---	---	168.8	74.8	82.0	0.7
C	---	---	0.0	69.4	100.0	7.8
D	---	---	0.0	45.1	100.0	40.1
E	---	---	0.0	35.8	100.0	52.5
F	---	---	0.0	0.0	100.0	100.0

T_i is the initial temperature of exothermic peak.; T_p is the peak temperature of exothermic peak

Table 2: DSC results of the Si-PTA resin at different curing stages

FTIR was employed to trace the curing reaction. As shown in Figure 3, absorption peaks of $\equiv\text{C-H}$ (3290 cm^{-1}) and $-\text{N}_3$, $-\text{C}\equiv\text{C}$ (2096 cm^{-1}) decreased gradually during the curing process, respectively. And a new small absorption peak at 3132 cm^{-1} , which is assigned to C-H in the triazole ring formed during the polymerization, occurred in the cured resin. It is indicated that the reaction between the azide and alkyne groups had taken place and the poly(1,2,3-triazole) has formed. After the resin was kept at $80^\circ\text{C}/12\text{ h} + 120^\circ\text{C}/2\text{ h} + 150^\circ\text{C}/2\text{ h} + 180^\circ\text{C}/2\text{ h} + 210^\circ\text{C}/2\text{ h} + 250^\circ\text{C}/2\text{ h}$, the absorption peaks at 2096 and 3290 cm^{-1} nearly disappeared, indicating that all the alkyne and azide groups have taken part in the cycloaddition polymerization. However, the peak at 2156 cm^{-1} did not vanish completely at the end of 250°C stage which was attributed to the residue internal ethynylene groups.

Figure 3: FTIR spectra of the Si-PTA resin at different stages of the curing:

Thermal properties of the cured resin

Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA) of the cured resin was carried out under air and DMA

curves are shown in Figure 4. As shown in Figure 4, the glass transition temperature (T_g) of the cured resin reached as high as 310 °C, owing to the high crosslinking density and the rigid molecular chain in the polymer. As shown in scheme 2, there are lots of benzene and triazole rings in the polymer and most of them are linked directly, resulting in the high rigidity of the molecular chain.

Figure 4: DMA curves of the cured Si-PTA resin

The thermal stability of the cured Si-PTA resin was determined by TGA. As shown in Figure 5, the decomposition process for the cured resin takes place in one stage under nitrogen but in two stages under air. The thermal decomposition temperature of the cured resin at 5 % weight loss (T_{d5}) under N_2 and air reached 342 °C and 340 °C, respectively. Two T_{d5} values are almost the same. This indicated that the Si-PTA resin exhibited good thermal and thermal oxidative stability. And due to the presence of weak C—N bonds, thermal oxidative decomposition was not a main process for the decomposition of the cured resin in the initial stage under air.

Figure 5: TGA curves of the cured Si-PTA resin

Mechanical properties of carbon fiber-reinforced Si-PTA resin composite

To optimize the preparation of composite materials and shorten the preparation cycle, the curing temperature was raised to 90 °C and the curing time was reduced to 6 h. Meanwhile, post-processing program was also changed. As shown in Table 3, the flexural strength and modulus reached 1678 MPa and 138 GPa, respectively. The composite also exhibited high flexural properties at high temperatures with the retention of the flexural strength reached 1095 MPa at 200°C. Therefore, the Si-PTA resin would be an excellent resin matrix for carbon fiber reinforced composites. Furthermore, the different procedures had little effect on the mechanical properties of the composite.

Test temperature	Sample	Flexural strength /MPa	Strength retention /%	Flexural modulus /GPa	ILSS /MPa
RT	A	1678	---	138	65.8
	B	1655	---	132	64.3
200°C	A	1095	65.3	131	---
	B	1084	65.5	130	---

Table 3: Mechanical properties of carbon fiber (T700)-reinforced Si-PTA resin composite prepared by different procedures (A: 80°C/12h+120°C/2h+150°C/2h+180°C/2h+210°C/2h+250°C/2h B: 90°C/6h+130°C/2h+170°C/3h+210°C/2h+250°C/2h)

Mechanical properties of the composite at different post-procedure stages were tested for further research. As shown in Table 4, the composite exhibited good mechanical properties after being cured at 90°C for 6 h, flexural strength could reach 1623 MPa. Then the flexural strength showed a downward trend after the first rise with elevating the treatment temperature. But the composite still retained good mechanical properties.

Post-procedure stages	Flexural strength /MPa	Flexural modulus /GPa	ILSS /MPa
90°C/6h	1623	140	70.6
90°C/6h+130°C/2h	1846	138	73.7
90°C/6h+130°C/2h+170°C/3h	1715	137	72.5
90°C/6h+130°C/2h+170°C/3h+210°C/2h	1638	135	64.1
90°C/6h+130°C/2h+170°C/3h+210°C/2h+250°C/2h	1665	132	64.3

Table 4: Mechanical properties of carbon fiber (T700)-reinforced Si-PTA resin composite at different post-procedure stages

Figure 6 shows the fractured section micrograph of a sample of the carbon fiber (T700)-reinforced Si-PTA resin composite. As shown in Figure 6, a rough surface of carbon fiber and a few evidence of fiber pullout are observed. The carbon fibers are well embedded in the Si-PTA resin. This indicates that there is good interface adhesion between the polytriazole resin and carbon fibers.

Fig.6: SEM image of carbon fiber (T700)-reinforced Si-PTA Resin composite

CONCLUSIONS

A new silico-polytriazole resin (Si-PTA) was prepared from DAMBP and LPSA by 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition polymerization. The LPSA was prepared by Grignard method and characterized by FT-IR and $^1\text{H-NMR}$. Viscosity-temperature curve showed that the Si-PTA good processability. According to DSC and FT-IR, the curing of Si-PTA resin underwent two stages with the increase of temperature. The cycloaddition of ethynyl and ethynylene with azides took place first at the temperature in the range of $90\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to $200\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, then the polymerization of ethynyl and ethynylene occurred at temperature in range of 240 to $280\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The cured Si-PTA resin exhibited good thermal properties as proved by TGA and DMA results. The glass transition temperature (T_g) of the cured resin reached $310\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and thermal decomposition temperature (T_{d5}) was 340 and $342\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in air and N_2 , respectively. The flexural strength of the carbon fiber (T700) reinforced composite reached 1678 MPa at room temperature and a property retention of 1095 MPa at $200\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, suggesting the Si-PTA resin could be expected to be a potential matrix for advanced composite materials.

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